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**INDO AMERICAN
 JOURNAL OF
 PHARMACEUTICAL
 RESEARCH**

PHARMACOVIGILANCE: AREAS TO REFORM

Surya Chandra. D, Akram Ahmad, Isha Patel¹, Krishna kanth.T, G.P. Mohanta, Parimalakrishnan. S*

*Department of Pharmacy Practice, Annamalai University, Annamalai nagar-608002, Tamilnadu, India
 Department of Clinical, Social and Administrative Sciences, University of Michigan at Ann Arbor, Ann Arbor, MI-48104, USA.¹*

ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 25 July 2012

Available online 30 July 2012

Keywords

Pharmacovigilance, Adverse Drug Reaction, Central drugs standard control organization.

ABSTRACT

Pharmacovigilance is growing in India. Given the size of the pharmaceutical market in India, it is important to understand how pharmacovigilance impacts the pharmaceutical products. Pharmacovigilance leads to the safe usage of the pharmaceutical drugs but under reporting is a major issue in India mainly due to lack of awareness or feeling of fear. In order to build a robust pharmacovigilance system in India, active participation would be required from the Indian pharma sector as well as the government. Initiatives that can assist the small privatized generic companies to cope with the evolving regulations given their limited budget, are necessary. This paper provides an overview about the current pharmacovigilance system in India, its problems and how the problems can be solved provided India follows the pharmacovigilance practices practiced by other developed and developing nations.

Corresponding author

Akram Ahmad, B.Pharm, PharmD Intern

Department of Pharmacy Practice, Annamalai University

Annamalai Nagar – 608002.Tamil Nadu, India.

Mob: +91-7358229769 E – Mail ID: akrampharma67@gmail.com

Please cite this article in press as: Akram Ahmad , Pharmacovigilance: Areas To Reform . Indo American Journal of Pharm Research. 2012:2(9).

Background:

India has witnessed a rapid development in provision of optimal conditions for conducting clinical trials, both in terms of resources and regulations. This development can be seen in the field of trials besides the pharma sector. Research and development is also developing at a rapid phase, boosting up the drug discovery in India. The advent of research and development in India has also increased the vulnerability to adverse drug reactions. This vulnerability led to the need for pharmacovigilance policies which didn't have a role among the previous generic policies adopted by pharmaceutical industries. The National Pharmacovigilance Programme was designed and made operational from January 1 2005. Even though majority of the regulations pertaining to pharmacovigilance were adopted from international policies like ICH and EU, there are some areas lacking clarity, that need reform and need to be paid special interest. In a resource constrained country such as India, this can be quite challenging since numerous factors need to be considered before making a regulation. The discussion below provides an overview of the pharmacovigilance system in India and compares it with regulatory areas in other nations so that appropriate reform can be brought about in India.^[3-7,14]

National Pharmacovigilance Program in India:

The National Pharmacovigilance Program (NPP) was launched by the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare in July 2010, primarily overseen by CDSCO, New Delhi. The program will be launched in five phases the details of which are given in Table 1. ADR reports collected from the AMCs will be dispatched to the national co-ordinating centre. The coordinating centre will conduct causality assessment and upload the reports into the pharmacovigilance software. Lastly, the integrated ADR data will be transmitted through vigiflow software interface into the Uppsala Monitoring Center's ADR database where signal processing will be carried out.^{23,24}

Table 1: Presented below is the roadmap for the Pharmacovigilance Programme of India. The programme will be implemented in five phases as depicted below:

Phase No.	Target for the five phases of pharmacovigilance program of India.	Description of national PVPI will be implemented in five phases as depicted below.
1	Initiation phase, 2010-2011	Developing systems and procedures, enrolling 40 medical colleges, distributing data collection forms, developing and establishing training centers, training people working in pharmacovigilance centers, linking with Uppasala monitoring centre in Sweden, initiating software development for national drug safety database, establishing zonal workshops for public awareness of drug safety and publishing drug safety news letter.
2	Expansion and consolidation phase 2011-2012	Enrolling additional 60 medical colleges, identifying gaps through training, training pharmacovigilance center employees to operate softwares provided by Uppasala monitoring centre, WHO.
3	Expansion and maintenance phase, 2012-2013	Enrolling additional 100 medical colleges, training of employees working in the pharmacovigilance centers, establishing zonal workshops for public awareness about drug safety and publishing drug safety news letter.

4	Expansion and optimization phase, 2013-2014	Enrolling additional 100 medical colleges, interacting with international pharmacovigilance bodies, establishing zonal workshops for public awareness about drug safety and publishing drug safety news letter.
5	Excellence phase, 2014-2015	Creating centre of excellence for pharmacovigilance in Asia Pacific region

Approach: There is a major difference in the approach followed by the developed and developing nations in framing the pharmacovigilance policies. While the policies in well-developed countries like US, UK, Japan are mainly focused on the management of the ADR, the policy in India mainly focuses on the collection and reporting of ADR. The approach used in India can be termed as “pharmacodiligance” and this approach does not satisfy the main objective of establishing a pharmacovigilance setup. It is the prime responsibility of the innovators i.e. the pharmaceutical companies, to continuously perform a risk benefit evaluation and mainly focus on risk management. However, majority of the pharma companies are generic. The Indian government finds it challenging to convince the pharma companies to change their approach since appropriate mechanism to differentiate the innovators from generics and frame regulations accordingly, is complicated.^[2,3]

Obligations:

Before discussing the policy framing issues, there are some important obligations that need to be addressed. These obligations are both clinical and industrial based. While maintaining the local operations, the nature of the obligations might be flexible or rigid.^[9,10] Some of the factors that influence the effective implementation of policy are discussed below:

Reporting:

There is lack of data on ADR reporting in India due to problems like under reporting, lack of transparency in the reports submitted by the industries, lack of differentiation between noise and signal, lack of awareness among health care professionals and lack of support from local governing bodies. Under reporting might be prevalent due to lack of knowledge about pharmacovigilance among the medical graduates and health care professionals. Medical institutions should provide information about pharmacovigilance in their curriculum to improve the knowledge base of the healthcare professionals. Some of the other reasons that can be attributed to underreporting include failure to detect, fear of damage to reputation, lack of training, lack of financial incentives, competency and feeling of guilt. Also in a country like India where use of traditional medicines is quite popular, the lack of vigilance while practicing the alternative systems of medicine such as Ayurveda, Homeopathy, Unani and Siddha is also a big problem.^[14-16]

Sensitivity:

Emotional sensitivity is an important factor to address as it affects prescribers, patient and companies. Patients or media may over react about any ADR that is reported on the drug without having the sound knowledge about the issue. Lack of understanding about the associated risk factors, relative risk and absolute risk may lead to many unexpected challenges in medical practice, especially in case of medications such as oral contraceptives. On many occasions, even physicians do not have sound knowledge about ADR reporting, its importance and avoid it due to their fear of damage to their reputation. Public perception that a company continuously reporting ADRs produces products of inferior quality than the company that reports to a lesser extent, is also quite common in India.^[1,2,5,21,15]

Collection of ADRs:

Presently, reporting ADRs is voluntary in many countries . In a country like India where most of the population is below poverty line and where literacy rate is not high, many are unfamiliar with pharmacovigilance related

terminologies and the procedure of reporting the same. Hence, there is a need to educate both the health care professionals and the people about the importance of ADR reporting. Contrary to the western world, where pharmacovigilance is practiced according to the set regulations, Indian health care professionals tend to be less motivated to practice the same. This indicates a strong need of provision of some sort of incentives to boost up the vigilance program in India.^[1,2,5,21,15]

Industrial prospect:

Pharmaceutical industries play an important role in forwarding pharmacovigilance by providing information about ADRs to the regulatory authorities through activities like signal detection, risk-benefit evaluation and risk management. It is not an easy job for industries to adhere to regulatory guidelines. Unfortunately industries encounter many problems in the process which require the attention of the regulatory authorities.^[2,10,19]

For generic companies:

Regulatory authorities or local governing bodies often see both the innovator and generic companies in the same light. It is mandatory for a generic company to adhere to the same regulations as an innovator company. Hence a generic company has to perform the base work associated with factors like cost and management to fulfill the pharmacovigilance related regulatory requirements.^[2,10]

Cost Implications:

Establishment of any setup requires capital investment. Some policies have to be maintained continuously as discontinuation may lead to serious consequences like penalties, product recalls, and consumer law suits, ultimately damaging the brand image. In order to maintain a good vigilance system, it is a must for any company to meet requirements such as software, medical dictionary for regulatory activities subscriptions, WHO drug dictionaries subscriptions, adequate manpower and efficient staff with good management skills. Also, access to a periodically updated health database is mandatory to get access to unbiased information. All the above factors require capital, which a generic company might find challenging to come up with.^[1-3,7]

Management issues:

There are many challenges in setting up a pharmacovigilance system including lack of resources and experts. A pharmacovigilance set up requires inputs from various departments such as regulatory affairs, information technology, sales, finance, marketing, legal, manufacturing, quality assurance, human resources, and third party vendors. These departments need to work in coordination to provide an effective output in areas like:

- 1) Customer call receipt and triage
- 2) ADR case processing & reporting (electronic or hard copy)
- 3) Periodic safety updates reporting (PSUR)
- 4) Product quality complaints management (included by some companies)
- 5) Medical inquiries management (included by some companies)
- 6) Electronic safety database validation
- 7) Safety data exchange agreement management
- 8) Signal detection – risk-benefit evaluation
- 9) Risk management programs
- 10) Literature monitoring for ADR case reports
- 11) Training of company employees on ADR reporting
- 12) Global compliance monitoring
- 13) Audits and inspections management

To ensure proper working of the above departments, a company needs huge capital investment if it plans to overlook the working of all the departments personally or it can outsource the job to CROs. Outsourcing is quite

popular now-a-days since the company can have assurance about the job being taken care of by the CROs as per the recommended regulations or guidelines.^[2,7,16,22,19]

Multinational operations:

Companies aspire to expand their activities globally for their personal development and in doing so, they have to obey local regulations. However, it is highly impossible to frame a pharmacovigilance policy that abides by every authority, for managing both the local and international operations. Hence, the very requirement of a universally acceptable harmonized pharmacovigilance policy. In countries like India and China, who are long time generic manufacturers, local bodies are forcing their industries to follow local regulations. But, these industries operate in many countries across the globe so; it is not possible to satisfy both local and international regulations simultaneously. Considering these requirements, it is inherent for an industry to either setup a pharmacovigilance department or to expand its existing capabilities.^[2,7]

Evolving Regulations:

Adherence to regulations is must for any company to continue its operations in any part of the world but evolving regulations present an ongoing challenge in terms of making changes to already well-established policies and resources. These evolving policies force any company to follow the newly established regulations. The companies might feel helpless since the evolving regulations are often accompanied by new problems. Companies in countries that have recently updated their regulations are listed below.^[2,10,19]

Table 2: Many countries recently updated their regulations^[22]

REGULATORY AGENCY	YEAR OF LAST UPDATE
Brazil	February 2009
Vietnam	March 2009
EU	Vol-9a September 2008
Russia	November 2008
US	Though CFR are final, however the guideline for post marketing pharmacovigilance was released in 2001 as a draft guideline.
Mexico	2007
Ukraine	2007

Funding:

Finance is always a major issue to address. Implementing a policy is more difficult compared to framing a policy and it requires a lot of investment, in terms of both human efforts and capital. Such investment is difficult cannot be successfully made possible in many countries. This factor can limit the number of pharmacovigilance centers to be established. Sources providing continuous support throughout the nation at all times, are necessary. The capital should be based on the population to be served by the center and support should be provided by institutions, insurance companies, government and other organizations which are health based.^[2,8]

Local governing bodies :

Local governing bodies play a key role in framing the pharmacovigilance policy mainly in countries, where the policy is still in the emerging phase. The pharmacovigilance system is well framed and very stringent in the US, Europe and Japan. So, regulations from such authorities should be considered while framing regulations in India. However, local bodies in India do not provide much freedom to committees for framing policies. Collaboration of the Indian governing bodies with international bodies should be encouraged in order to frame the necessary policies.^[2,16]

Harmonized pharmacovigilance:

Need for harmonization: Although common regulations are framed, differences in ideology still persist in different regions, creating challenges for companies to perform their activities. The ultimate goal of these regulations is to provide a uniform and standard platform to the industries to carry out their activities effectively and share the collected information through a database so that it is possible to reap collective benefits. [2,7,10,16]

Table 3: Variations in regulations [22,25]

S.NO.	ACTIVITY	VARIATIONS	EXAMPLES
Start of Pharmacovigilance responsibilities for a product			
1	Pharmacovigilance obligations start date	From date of authorization From date of launch of product in the market	US, Canada, EU India, Australia (expedited reporting)
Variations in Expedited reporting standards			
2	Timelines for submission	15 calendar days 10 working days for domestic cases 5 calendar days	US, EU Vietnam business partner exchange
3	Requirement for foreign/ domestic reports	Both foreign and domestic Foreign reports not required	US, EU, Japan, Ukraine (Only serious unexpected, fatal/ life threatening cases from confirmed company products Mexico, South Africa, Malaysia, Brazil, Australia, Singapore, Thailand, China, Russia
4	Medically confirmed versus unconfirmed cases	Accepted not accepted	US EU
5	Published Literature monitoring for ADR cases	Required not required	US, EU, Australia (domestic only), Canada, Japan India, Latin America, Africa, Russia, CIS
6	Different ADR reporting forms	Med Watch/ Council for International Organizations of Medical Sciences or CIOMS (for foreign cases only) CIOMS	US
7	Electronic (E2B) reporting requirement	Mandatory	Japan EU Competent Authorities and European Medicines Agency (EMA)

		not mandatory	rest of world
Differences in Periodic reporting standards			
8	PSUR submission Requirements	Mandatory requirement On request by regulatory agencies At license renewal only	US, EU, India Canada, South Africa United Arab Emirates
9	PSUR submission cycles	Quarterly, annually Quarterly, semi-annually, annually, re-registration	US Mexico
		Three years (harmonized birth date based) Annually Registration, re-registration	EU Australia Kazakhstan, Ukraine, Russia, Belarus, Iran, UAE, China
10	Content of PSUR	The following sections of a PSUR are not required: patient exposure, literature search, detailed marketing authorization status Comprehensive data is required per volume 9A, including all sections listed above Literature search not required Additional requirement of write up about company's pharmacovigilance systems Additional requirement of executive summary in Portuguese. PSUR content can be in English	US EU India Kazakhstan Brazil
11	Timelines for submission of PSUR from the Data Lock Point (DLP)	30 – 60 days (quarterly/annual) 60 days 30 days	US EU, brazil India
Variations in Risk Management Plan/Program requirements			
12	Risk management program e.g., Isotretinoin risk management	iPledge program mandatory Not mandated by any other agency	US, Canada, EU Rest of the world
13	Risk management plan submission mandatory	For all new registrations Not mandatory for all registrations	EU Rest of the world

Table 4: Variations in Information Dissemination^[12,23]

COUNTRIES	INFORMATION DISEMMINATION
Australia	Regular bulletins are published
Brazil	Conducting training and courses for health care team by national agencies
India	In the form of published reports
Jordan	Workshops for health care teams in both public and private sector
Malaysia	Manuals, talks, publications in official newsletter Berita-ubat-ubatan
Singapore	Newsletters and published reports
South Africa	As official document like gazette
Ukraine	Information bulletins are prepared and recommendations are made to health professionals, investigators and health ministry

Table 5: Variations in Regulatory Action Taken^[12,23]

COUNTRY	REGULATORY ACTION TAKEN
Australia	Withdrawal from market or modification of contraindications, warnings, precaution to product
Brazil	Identifying the global scenario of drug withdrawals, specially on drugs with irrational active ingredient combinations, products requiring restrictions and with no therapeutic value and implementing changes accordingly
India	Suggest to regulatory for intervention related to drug/class
Jordan	Required changes to be introduced in product information
Malaysia	Making changes to product information, contraindications, precautions, warnings and also to dosages and in advertising material
Singapore	When ADRs occur more frequently than previously expected then changes are to be made in marketing authorization and when it leads to effects that are unacceptable it is withdrawn from market
South Africa	Changes to product information or labeling
Ukraine	Center shall propose to ministry of health to take decision regarding temporary or permanent ban on product until further trials result in disapproval of the unsafe properties of the drug

Areas to review:

Compared to the regulations prevalent in different countries with regards to the timeline for submission of PSUR, the content to be included in PSUR, risk management strategy, information dissemination and the regulatory actions performed as part of the Indian pharmacovigilance programme need changes in different aspects such as

- 1) Literature search not being presently required for submission of PSUR, even though it improves the possibility to search for a possible new ADR.
- 2) Informing about the PV policy in Kazakhstan to the Indian regulatory bodies as it will provide information about their policies and allow for improvement of Indian policies.

- 3) Adoption of electronic reporting system due to its established superiority in other fields.
- 4) Mandatory implementation of ipledge like EU since it will enable us to come out with a robust pharmacovigilance plan with a main focus on risk management.
- 5) Inclusion of updated risk management plan in periodic submission.
- 6) Issuing an acknowledgement receipt with a reference number for all further correspondence to avoid any duplication of reports. There should be timely and easy feedback for all the cases reported.
- 7) Harmonizing the conditions for approval of drugs with phase IV clinical trial data to enable safety evaluation, contrary to the present process of approval based on special conditions like finalization. Sharing of information should be encouraged.
- 8) Reporting of ADRs to limit the confidentiality of the investigator and avoiding the involvement of the media and the patient, in addition to informing the safety issues of the drugs.
- 9) Taking regulatory action after receiving a signal similar to the process employed in Ukraine since delaying in decision making may put the patient's health at risk.
- 10) Disseminating information similar to Brazil and Jordan since making the information public and providing recommendations to the health ministry will have more beneficial effects.
- 11) Introducing ADR monitoring and reporting issues in school and college curriculum and combining ADR monitoring with public health programmes.^[14,20,22,21]

Implementing all the above factors might be challenging to the companies since there is an immense need to employ a universally acceptable harmonized pharmacovigilance system. Such a system should be governed by a universal body like UPPASALA that has links with local organizations all over the globe. This will also allow more companies to carry out their pharmacovigilance activities without much difficulty. Thus, a more active vigilance programme can be constructed than the previous one. Harmonization, similar to globalization can lead to the formation of a more widely accepted programme that can ensure good progress.

Conclusion:

Patient safety is the ultimate goal of pharmacovigilance regulatory agencies. Hence, it is important to consider factors that create barriers for various stakeholders in the system in framing regulations that promote patient well-being. It is also the responsibility of the regulatory agencies to be more actively involved in conducting educational campaigns for both the health care teams and the people since under reporting of medication errors/adverse drug events is a major hindrance. Harmonizing regulations enables more industries to actively indulge and share required information among the healthcare community. Educating the healthcare professionals will enable the pharma companies avoid sensitivity. Minor differences can be negotiated by considering the local conditions of particular members. In developing countries, incentives can be helpful for encouraging people to report.

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